

CLASSICA

Validating AI in classifying cancer in real-time surgery

Report on potential obstacles and solutions

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Executive Summary

The Horizon Europe CLASSICA project aims to clinically validate an AI-based technology for identifying and analysing cancer tumours. Validation will be carried out across several clinical sites, surgical teams, and countries.

Tumour tissue has significantly different vasculature from healthy tissue, and irregular angiogenesis is a hallmark of tumour development. In CLASSICA, our technology uses rapid analysis of tissue fluorescence dynamics to differentiate between cancerous and non-cancerous tissues. In essence, the fluorescence intensity of pixels displaying tissues of interest varies with blood flow (perfusion) when the blood is dyed with fluorescent indocyanine green (ICG) and lit by near-infrared (NIR) light. The fluorescence intensity (FI) is captured over time from multiple video frames and plotted as a curve. The intensity curves of tumour tissue differ from those of healthy tissue, and those of benign tumours differ from malignant ones. Analysis of the curve features for each pixel in a region of interest can thus lead to a classification.

This deliverable is an output of Task 3.3, “Blockers and facilitators” and follows D3.1 “Training Report” to which it is strictly interlinked, as it reports from previously completed tasks concerning the creation of training material and its delivery.

This task was carried out with a focus group of surgeons recruited by EAES and surgical training attendees to explore blockers and facilitators for using CLASSICA in the OR. The activity will be implemented as a series of two workshops – one before CLASSICA training and one after training- to assess the impact of training and experience. The first workshop took place at the EAES Annual Congress event in Maastricht in June 2024. The second will take place at the EAES Annual Congress event in Belgrad in June 2025.

The present deliverable is considered to be the conclusive report of WP3, drawing conclusions and summarising all the experiences of the previous tasks, which has been finalised and addressed by the mean of two workshops held as part of the EAES annual meeting in Rome 2023 and Maastricht 2024. Special consideration was paid to these two workshops as the final part of WP3 “Training and Clinical Implementation Analysis”.

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List of acronyms, definitions and abbreviations

AI	Artificial Intelligence
CRC	Colorectal Cancer
DTIF	Disruptive Technologies Innovation Fund
DoA	Description of Action
FI	Fluorescence intensity
ICG	Indocyanine Green
NIR	Near-infrared
OR	Operating Room
WP	Work Package

1 Introduction

CLASSICA will deliver and clinically validate an artificial intelligence (AI)-based decision support technology, which enables rapid identification of the presence and distribution of rectal cancer tumours. Clinical validation will be carried out across several institutions, surgical teams, and countries.

The technology uses rapid analysis of tissue fluorescence dynamics to differentiate between cancerous and non-cancerous tissues. It has been applied in colorectal cancer (CRC) and transanal surgery and has demonstrated excellent accuracy in distinguishing between cancerous and healthy tissue. Essentially, the fluorescence intensity (FI) of pixels displaying tissues of interest varies with blood flow (perfusion) when a commercially available fluorescent dye named indocyanine green (ICG) is systemically administered and excited using a near-infrared (NIR) light. The FI is then captured over time from multiple video frames, and this intensity is plotted as a curve. Intensity curves for tumour tissue differ from those of healthy tissue, and those of benign tumours differ from malignant ones. Analysis of the curve features for each pixel in a region of interest can subsequently lead to an AI-based classification.

The specific objectives of the project are to:

- Deploy and perform clinical validation studies across five clinical sites in Ireland, Belgium, Austria, Italy, and the Netherlands.
- Assess the usability, safety, and performance of the CLASSICA system.
- Agree upon standard operating protocols for implementing and using the CLASSICA system.
- Develop and deliver training for CLASSICA tissue classification tools during biopsy and surgery.
- Develop new guidelines to help guide the use of AI for surgical decision support.

The project builds on breakthrough research by the Irish DTIF Consortium, comprising UCD, RCSI, and IBM Research. The project developed a novel research premise that will be optimised and validated in the CLASSICA project.

As the CLASSICA software being validated in this project is deployed within a clinical method, as a consequence of the fulfilment of the first steps dealing with training outlined in WP3 (creating training resources and developing and standardising the clinical protocol among the collaborating clinical centres), we focused on the following objectives:

- Assessment of possible blockers and facilitators for the use of CLASSICA in the OR following the conclusion of the workshop
- Evaluation of other possible applications of AI in surgery and AI-related issues in surgery
- Evaluation of possible solutions

This deliverable focuses on Task 3.3 'Blockers and Facilitators'.

2 Events and Results

Task 3.3, “Blockers and Facilitators”, involved organising two events scheduled as part of the EAES annual meetings, held in Rome (2023) and Maastricht (2024).

Additionally, these congresses provided an opportunity for the EAES Task Force, composed of members from the EAES Technology Committee with expertise in AI and fluorescence, to consult with each other on the CLASSICA programme.

At both events, a designated exhibition space was set up to showcase information about the CLASSICA project, promoting its achievements and gathering feedback. To support this, a banner was produced and displayed in the Technology Corner, specifically designed for this purpose. Photos from the exhibitions were shared on social media and within the CLASSICA group.

2.1 Artificial Intelligence Masterclass, EAES Annual Congress Rome June 2023

The masterclass featured a scientific component, was open to all EAES members and local surgeons, and focused on the use of AI, with presentation of the CLASSICA Project.

MC4 Artificial Intelligence (by technology committee)

Masterclass directors: Felix Nickel (Germany), Chen Sagiv (Israel), Pietro Mascagni (Italy)

Faculty: Ronan Cahill (Ireland), Pieter de Backer (Belgium), Martin Wagner (Germany), Roi Anteby (Israel), Young-Woo Kim (Korea), Vinkle Srivastav (France), Deepak Alapatt (France), Joël Lavanchy (France)

Room: Sydney

09.00 - 17.30 hrs

Session 1: Surgery 4.0 / Digital surgery

09:00 - 09.30 Tactile internet in surgery - Martin Wagner (Germany)

09:30 - 10.00 Surgical robotics as a key platform - Pieter de Backer (Belgium)

10:00 - 10.30 AI in surgery: State of the art - Roi Anteby (Israel) (remote)

10.30 -11.00 Coffee break

Session 2: AI fundamentals

11:00 - 11.30 Intro to coding - Vinkle Srivastav (France)

11:30 - 12.00 Intro to ML and DL - Chen Sagiv (Israel)

12:00 - 12.30 Intro to CV - Deepak Alapatt (France)

12.30 - 13.30 Lunch break

Session 3: Surgical AI

13:30 - 14.00 Annotation - Joël Lavanchy (France)

14:00 - 14.30 Applications - Ronan Cahill (Ireland)

14:30 - 15.00 Clinical translation - Pietro Mascagni (Italy)

15:00 - 15.30 Ethical, cultural, and educational considerations - Young-Woo Kim (Korea)

15.30 - 16.00 Coffee break

Session 4: Hands on

16.00 - 16.30 Imaging sensor: Spectral Imaging - Felix Nickel (Germany), Amila Cizmic (Germany)

16.30 - 17.00 Annotations: Endoscopic videos / images - Martin Wagner (Germany), Joel Lavanchy (Switzerland)

17.00 - 17.30 Coding a simple application: tool detection - Vinkle Srivastav (France), Deepak Alapatt (France)

Audience we are aiming to attract:

-Surgeons of any age, residents, medical students interested in getting more basic knowledge on AI research and applications in surgery including some practical exposure to surgical AI

Programme (1 day):

-Basic introduction to AI including core terms and different architectures of important models,

-overview of 1. Sensors /Data, 2. AI Models, 3. AI Tasks, 4. AI Applications, 5. Outcomes, 6. Successful clinical use of AI in surgery

-Practical exercises with AI applications, participants are encouraged to bring their own device (Laptop) and also their own data (surgical video or CT scan) for live experience of annotation, labelling etc.

The workshop was held in front of 103 registered attendees.

The CLASSICA system, featuring an updated algorithm for the diagnosis and treatment of early rectal cancer, was showcased. The discussion following the presentations provided insights into the potential applications of the technology. Moreover, liability concerns were thoroughly examined with the support of an international expert. Finally, a comprehensive overview was provided on how this technology could be applied not only to other surgical procedures but also more broadly across the medical field.

Conclusions were that CLASSICA represents a very interesting innovation which may represent a real breakthrough in the diagnosis and treatment of early rectal cancer. When available on flexible endoscopes, this should become the ideal method to assess the primary tumour (benign or malignant) of all GI tract lesions - following proper validation. It is crucial to confirm the reliability of initial findings, which will be addressed in Study 2 of CLASSICA, where biopsies will be guided by AI analysis of the lesions. If successful, this could introduce a new approach that may eventually replace traditional biopsies, using ICG and AI analysis. Today, the absence of ICG-NIR cameras on flexible endoscopes limits this application in clinical practice, but this is a challenge that is both theoretically and technically solvable.

2.2 CLASSICA Webinar, in cooperation with IRCAD, March 2024

A webinar was organised in collaboration with IRCAD, EAES and the broader CLASSICA team. The webinar focused on “validating AI in classifying cancer in real-time surgery”. 95 registered viewers

watched the webinar live, and it has been viewed 531 times on WebSurg since it was published on the website¹. It was held on March 26, 2024, and featured the following program:

Tuesday, March 26 | 2:00 - 3:30pm (UTC+1)

- 2:00-2:05**
Introduction
Chairs: Alberto AREZZO (IT), Ronan Cahill (IR), Pietro Mascagni (IT), Rita Rodriguez (MX), Silvana Perretta (IT)
- 2:05-2:20**
State-of-the-art treatment for rectal cancer polyps
Felix Aigner (AU)
- 2:20-2:35**
Biophysics-inspired artificial intelligence for colorectal cancer characterization
Alice Moynihan (IR)
- 2:35-2:50**
Validating AI in classifying cancer in real-time surgery
Ronan Cahill (IR)
- 2:50-3:05**
Liability and legal concerns when using AI decision support in the OR
Mindy Nunez Duffourc (US)
- 3:05-3:20**
Guidance and training in the intraoperative use of AI
Pietro Mascagni (IT)
- 3:20-3:30**
Panel Discussion & Concluding remarks

Free of charge - Registration mandatory

Please note that this online course/webinar will be recorded solely for broadcasting purposes. Your participation in the meeting involves your acceptance of being recorded, with respect to GDPR regulations.

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Figure 1 Program of CLASSICA Webinar, in collaboration with IRCAD, in front of 109 registered attendees.

This event brought together experts and practitioners for a comprehensive discussion on the future of cancer treatment. This webinar gathered a panel of experts delving into the state-of-the-art rectal

¹ <https://websurg.com/fr/doi/wb01en7312>

polyp treatment, biophysics-inspired AI for colorectal cancer characterisation, liability, and legal concerns when using AI decision support in the operating room (OR), and guidance and training in intraoperative use. The final panel discussion helped us understand current possible indications for using CLASSICA technology along the entire GI tract, changing the paradigm in treating early disease. This includes both upper and lower GI tract lesions, with a particular focus on esophageal and rectal cancers, which present significant challenges today in achieving optimal staging and treatment.

Additionally, the potential for combining this technology with sentinel node sampling was examined. The rectum, considered a distinct organ with its own lymphatic drainage system, has sentinel lymph nodes located primarily within the mesorectum. Recent MRI-based research has confirmed that in almost 100% of cases, the sentinel lymph node is located below the primary rectal tumour. Therefore, transrectal excision of the primary tumour would expose the mesorectal tissue where these sentinel lymph nodes are actually located. Using fluorescence to highlight the sentinel lymph nodes would be ideal for their identification, allowing for more accurate staging of the lymph nodes (N) after determining the tumour stage (T) based on the rectal wall excision [1] [2]. This would represent a major step forward over the current situation, where the reliability of Endoscopic Ultrasound (EUS) in assessing T is around 60%, with 20% of cases being overstaged and 20% understaged. EUS provides only a risk stratification of potential disease extension to lymph nodes, indicating whether the cancer is loco-regional rather than strictly local. Achieving more accurate staging with sentinel lymph node identification could revolutionise rectal cancer treatment, similar to the shift seen in breast cancer treatment during the 1980s and 1990s.

Figure 2 Webinar screenshot

2.3 CLASSICA Workshop, EAES Annual Congress Maastricht June 2024

The workshop in Maastricht, held on Tuesday, June 11, attracted 125 participants. The workshop focused on areas of discomfort, specifically exploring why surgeons might be hesitant to adopt AI-driven decision support tools and how their concerns could be effectively addressed.

The program was organised as follows:

D3.2 Report on potential obstacles and solutions

WS3 Workshop Classica

Course directors: Ronan Cahill (Ireland), Alberto Arezzo (Italy)

15.00 - 17.00 hrs Room: Volga 2.1

Chair: Ronan Cahill (Ireland)

15.00 - 15.20 Local excision for neoplasia - state of the art - Jurriaan Tuynman (The Netherlands)

15.20 - 15.40 Classica project - state of the future art - Ronan Cahill (Ireland)

15.40 - 16.10 Classica software - hands-on demo - Samo Erzen (Slovenia)

16.10 - 16.30 AI and surgery - liability issues - Mindy Nunez Duffourc (The Netherlands)

16.30 - 17.00 AI and surgery - quo vadis? - Alberto Arezzo (Italy) (EAES)

Figure 3 Prof. Alberto Arezzo giving the presentation - AI and surgery - quo vadis? at the Workshop Classica in front of 125 registered attendees.

A focus group of EAES member surgeons provided a broader external perspective, raising key issues that the newly trained CLASSICA surgeons could address through an active-learning approach.

While CLASSICA was the central focus, the workshop also considered other possible applications of AI in surgery, discussing the challenges these might encounter and how to overcome them. The EAES Task Force (Mascagni, Nickel, Sagiv) thoroughly examined this aspect through a further workshop dealing

with AI issues, on Friday, June 14th 2024, as a post-congress event, after the Annual Congress itself, in Maastricht.

Discussions with the audience and experts external to CLASSICA confirmed the findings from previous events, i.e. the paradigm shift in the workup of early rectal cancer, the possible extension to the entire GI tract, with particular relevance to the esophagus, and the technically possible embedding of this technology into standard endoscopes, to move the assessment to the diagnostic phase. A live hands-on demonstration of the technology at its current stage of development was provided. The discussion also focused on liability issues, an area generating significant debate, especially in healthcare. It was emphasised how AI applications, including CLASSICA, could optimise resources, which are often insufficient to meet all healthcare demands. Here, CLASSICA has the potential to simplify the workup process, making it both faster and more precise, allowing for quicker and more accurate treatment decisions.

In parallel, the CLASSICA team carried out training as part of the project programme. After completing training for CLASSICA Study 1, surgical staff from each site were well-equipped to explore potential barriers to the adoption of CLASSICA and ways to address them. For example, one consideration was determining the acceptable duration for assessing the entire lesion at the start of the surgical/endoscopic procedure. It was also noted that performing such diagnostic assessments before treatment might be more effective, possibly using a different type of flexible endoscope. Additionally, it was observed that the procedure requires absolute camera steadiness, which could pose a challenge if the assessment is prolonged. Moreover, ensuring the bowel is completely clean is crucial to prevent the need for intraoperative cleaning, which often results in bleeding and would interfere with accurate assessments.

2.4 MC4 Artificial Intelligence Masterclass, EAES Annual Congress Maastricht June 2024

A masterclass on Artificial Intelligence (MC4) was organised as part of the EAES annual meeting 2024 in Maastricht on Friday, June 14, with 38 registered participants. Directed by Felix Nickel, Chen Sagiv, and Pietro Mascagni, the session ran from 09:00 to 17:30.

The first part of the programme explored digital surgery, with talks on surgical data science by Pietro Mascagni, surgical robotics as a key platform by Pieter de Backer, and AI-driven surgical quality assessment by Felix Nickel. This was followed by a presentation on ethical, cultural, and educational considerations by Young-Woo Kim.

The later session concentrated on developing AI, with Deepak Alapat discussing surgical computer vision, Luca Sestini covering practical considerations for surgical AI, and Ronan Cahill concluding the day with a presentation titled 'Making CLASSICA,' which delved into the development and applications of the CLASSICA project in surgical AI."

The program was organised as follows:

MC4 Artificial Intelligence

Masterclass directors: Felix Nickel (Germany), Chen Sagiv (Israel), Pietro Mascagni (Italy)

Faculty: Ronan Cahill (Ireland), Pieter de Backer (Belgium), Young-Woo Kim (Korea), Luca

Sestini

(France), Deepak Alapat (France)

Room: Sydney 0.10

09.00 - 17.30 hrs

Session 1: Digital Surgery

09:00 - 09:30 Surgical data science - Pietro Mascagni (Italy)

09:30 - 10:00 Surgical robotics as a key platform - Pieter de Backer (Belgium)

10:00 - 10:30 Surgical quality assessment with AI - Felix Nickel (Germany)

10:30 - 10:45 Ethical, cultural, and educational considerations - Young-Woo Kim (Korea)

10.45 - 11:15 **Coffee break**

Session 2: Developing AI

11:15 - 11:45 Surgical computer vision - Deepak Alapat (France)

11:45 - 12:15 Surgical AI: practical considerations - Luca Sestini (France)

12:15 - 12:45 Making CLASSICA - Ronan Cahill (Ireland)

Figure 4 Felix Nickel (DE), Chen Sagiv (IL), Pietro Mascagni (IT) chair MC4 Artificial Intelligence in front of 38 registered attendees

The workshop concluded with a focus on the current and future perspectives of the CLASSICA Project. After a detailed discussion on practical considerations for using surgical AI, attention shifted to the Training and Validation of AI systems in Luca Sestini's (IRCAD) presentation. Ronan Cahill then introduced the audience, now well-versed in the state-of-the-art in AI and surgery, to the key aspects

of the CLASSICA Project. This included the presentation of the concept and preliminary results from CLASSICA Study 1. The session featured a panel discussion with Task Force members and renowned experts in minimally invasive surgery and education, such as George Hanna (President of the EAES and Chief of Surgery at Imperial College London) and Nader Francis (Internal Auditor of the EAES and Chief of the Griffin Institute London – robot & MIS training facility).

Conclusions of the masterclass included the potential of AI applications in healthcare. CLASSICA, in particular, was discussed alongside other image analysis techniques that do not incorporate ICG absorption—an important factor in distinguishing benign, early, and invasive neoplasms. CLASSICA was presented as practical advancement in the field of AI and imaging. The audience agreed that while using AI for treatment purposes is still premature, image analysis is expected to become a prominent field for AI applications in the near future.

3 Impact & Conclusion

Interactions with the CLASSICA Task Force have been successfully facilitated through a series of initiatives, including a session in Rome and a masterclass in Maastricht, as well as webinars and masterclasses at the EAES Annual Events. These events, which gathered over a hundred participants, allowed for extensive collaboration and discussion on key issues, particularly around the use of AI in surgery.

Notably, we organised two workshops that specifically addressed concerns regarding the use of AI in the OR. Additionally, a dedicated session on AI's role within the CLASSICA project provided an opportunity for in-depth discussions, facilitating effective confrontation and exploration of AI-related challenges and opportunities in surgical practice.

Importantly, these discussions raised potential challenges in the operating room, providing valuable insights. The Task Force's proactive engagement, alongside input from trained surgeons, led to practical solution-centred discussions.

In addition, media from these activities were shared across social platforms, further enhancing the project's visibility within the surgical community.

Training under WP3 also played an important role. Thanks to the standardisation of the capture of ICG-perfusion patterns across clinical sites, facilitated through training, analyses gained consistency and reliability. This helped to address a potential obstacle related to the use of AI in the operating room, by creating a more consistent and manageable framework for surgeons to work with. Training and agreement of protocols are essential steps to ensure any questions or concerns from surgeons can be addressed effectively.

The results from Task 3.3 are entirely transferable to Studies 2 and 3. Training developed in WP3 will help surgeons in using CLASSICA-OR intraoperatively for biopsy and resection procedures using simulated and observed cases.

Through the establishment of the Task Force and continued engagement with external stakeholders, the CLASSICA team is committed to providing a space for open dialogue, where concerns can be raised and addressed promptly. This ongoing communication will help resolve any potential obstacles, facilitating the broader uptake of the project results. For this reason, a permanent Task Force was

established at EAES in order to provide a broader external viewpoint by a focus group of six EAES member-surgeons, who will be expected to raise issues that the newly-trained CLASSICA surgeons can address in an active-learning approach. Further insights will be compiled at the next Workshop / Masterclass to be organised in Belgrad at the Annual Congress of EAES in June 2025, with results reported in the next Periodic Report.

We can summarise the following:

1. CLASSICA represents a very interesting innovation which may represent a real breakthrough in the diagnosis and treatment of early rectal cancer.
2. When available on flexible endoscopes, this could become the ideal way to assess the primary tumour (benign or malignant) of all GI tract lesions.
3. It will be crucial to confirm the reliability of our preliminary findings to date. This will be achieved in CLASSICA Study 2, in which we will direct biopsies depending on the AI analysis of the lesion.
4. Upon completion of the CLASSICA project, we expect to have a novel tool with the potential to replace biopsies in the workup.
5. ICG – NIR cameras on flexible endoscopes represent a limit of the application in the workup, but this is theoretically and technically solvable.
6. The potential for combining this technology with sentinel node sampling introduces new possibilities for stratifying the risk of disease extension to lymph nodes. This opens the door to important new strategies in the treatment of rectal cancer, similar to the advances seen in breast cancer treatment during the 1980s and 1990s.

References

- [1] A. Arezzo, S. Arolfo, M. Mistrangelo, B. Mussa, P. Cassoni and M. Morino , “Transrectal sentinel lymph node biopsy for early rectal cancer during transanal endoscopic microsurgery,” *Minim Invasive Ther Allied Technol*, vol. 23, no. 1, pp. 17-20, 2014.
- [2] C. Ammirati , A. Arezzo, C. Gaetani , G. A. Strazzarino, R. Faletti, L. Bergamasco, F. Barisone, P. Fonio and M. Morino, “Can we apply the concept of sentinel lymph node in rectal cancer surgery?,” *Minim Invasive Ther Allied Technol*, pp. 1-7, 2024.